

Death toll exceeds 20,000 across Europe in June 2026 heat wave

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The June 2026 heat wave was the most extreme heat event ever experienced in Europe. Using previously developed heat-mortality response functions, I calculate that June 22-28 saw 20,390 heat-related deaths across Europe. This result highlights the accelerating threat of mass heat mortality events in Europe despite previous adaptations to heat.

In June 2026, temperature records were shattered across many areas of Europe, driven by a persistent atmospheric high-pressure system¹. Temperatures reached their all-time highs across many stations in the UK, Spain, France, Germany, and other countries.

Heat is dangerous to human health. Europe has experienced significant heat mortality in previous summers, most notably in 2003²⁻⁴ and more recently 2022⁵ and 2024⁶. While adaptation actions following 2003 were successful in reducing mortality in later summers such as 2006⁷, the potential for mass heat mortality has remained substantial, especially as climate change increases the intensity of the heat experienced from a given set of weather conditions⁸.

These previous episodes, and the record-breaking nature of the June 2026 heat wave, motivate an assessment of the Europe-wide death toll of this event. I apply previously developed statistical methods⁸ for modeling heat-related mortality across more than 900 subnational regions of Europe over 2015–2019. This approach regresses weekly mortality rates on weekly sums of nonlinear daily temperature terms, controlling for region-specific trends and seasonality in temperature and mortality. Critically, even though the mortality data is aggregated weekly, using summed daily terms can recover the nonlinear effects of individual days^{9,10}.

Results show that mortality risk rises rapidly as daily maximum temperatures increase (Fig. 1c). Days above 40 °C cause a >6% increase in weekly mortality rates compared with days around 25 °C. In most cases, warmer regions in Europe appear less vulnerable to heat, consistent with evidence of adaptation – but this pattern reverses for days above 40 °C, with warmer regions experiencing greater mortality risk, potentially indicating fundamental limits to adaptation (Fig. 1a).

Using this fitted model, I compare temperatures observed in the weeks of June 2026 to their corresponding climatological averages over 1991-2020, quantifying the increase in mortality associated with experiencing the actual heat wave compared with this counterfactual seasonal cycle⁵.

The June 2026 heat wave was associated with 20,390 excess deaths across Europe (Fig. 1b) (95% confidence interval: 17,201 – 25,141). The vast majority of the deaths likely occurred during the week of June 22-28, when temperatures peaked at above 40 °C across many countries. Over space, the greatest mortality was estimated in France (5,210), Germany (4,543), Spain (3,163), and Italy (2,709) (Fig. 1c).

These results are qualitatively consistent with on-the-ground reports of excess mortality in Europe. For example, the French health authorities reported more than 1,000 excess deaths between June 24

and 27, noting that this total was expected to rise substantially with greater surveying and reporting of mortality in the coming days¹¹. Importantly, the statistical model used in this study tracks the effect of heat on overall all-cause mortality, without needing to rely on explicit coding of heat as a cause of death on death certificates.

An open question in heat mortality work is whether heat in spring or early summer is more dangerous than heat that occurs later in the summer, when people may be more acclimatized to heat. On the other hand, some of the most devastating heat waves such as 2003 occurred in August rather than early summer. Accounting for the differential effects of heat in different parts of the spring, summer, and fall is an important research priority and may alter these results.

Increasing extreme heat, and resulting mortality, is the consequence of global warming driven by fossil fuel emissions. Every ton of CO₂ emitted appreciably increases global average temperature and thus local heat extremes¹². Given the continued increase in fossil fuel emissions and the potential for extreme events even if humanity undertakes rapid decarbonization¹³, significant increases in adaptation investments will be necessary to reduce future heat mortality. Understanding which adaptations to heat are most empirically successful and can be scaled rapidly is thus a critical research priority¹⁴.

Figure 1: Heat-related mortality in Europe in June 2026. a) Relationship between daily maximum temperature and weekly mortality rates across Europe, estimated by Callahan et al.⁸. The effect of temperature and mortality is allowed to vary as a function of baseline mean temperature, and curves are plotted at the average temperatures of three terciles of regional average temperatures. b) Europe-wide heat-related mortality in three weeks from June 8 to 28. Error bars shows 90% confidence intervals based on uncertainty in heat-mortality response. c) Region-specific heat-related mortality rates (deaths per 100,000 population) in the week of June 22-28. White regions are those without continuous mortality data.

Methods Summary

The majority of the details of the statistical heat-mortality model are given in Callahan et al.⁸. For this study, the fitted coefficients for the model with daily high temperature as the independent variable are taken directly from that study's replication materials. 3 weekly lags are included to track the delayed effects of heat.

To calculate the death toll of June 2026 heat, ERA5 reanalysis data are downloaded for 2026 up through June 24, and spliced with GFS forecast data for June 24 to 28 (similar to Keeping et al.¹). These data are then aggregated to NUTS3 regions across Europe, weighting spatially by population, and aggregated to weekly nonlinear sums of temperature to match the panel data used in the previous study⁸. These temperatures are then compared to the 1991-2020 mean for each corresponding week and the percent change in mortality rate is calculated. The percent change in the mortality rate is multiplied by the 2015-2019 baseline number of deaths in the corresponding week and NUTS3 region to calculate total numbers of deaths.

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